

Dominican SnapGuide: An interactive e-manual for basic and digital photography class

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Abstract

The researchers proposed “Dominican SnapGuide: An Interactive E-Manual for Basic and Digital Photography Class” to experiment more enhancement of a user manual with interactions, animation, two-dimensional photographs, and buttons to navigate. The researchers created the interactive E-manual exclusively for the upcoming students who will be enrolling to basic and digital photography, the project was based on the St. Dominic College of Asia (SDCA) ’s course syllabus where the project has the first to fifth weeks of the lesson of the certain subject. It has an interactive buttons where the user can navigate and skip any pages. It also has a layout of a digital single-lens reflex (DSLR) camera where the user can navigate each part and function.

Keywords: E-learning, e-manual, interactive, manual, photography.

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Introduction

Photography is also a kind of way of how the photographer shows the emotion through photographs. Visual records created by an impression of light on a variety of light-sensitive surfaces, photographs are being created. A photograph also means “drawing with light”. Many practitioners and historians would argue that photography belongs under the art, craft, and design general certificate of secondary education (GCSE) and A level standards, preferring to think of it as a vocational discipline (Nicholls, 2016).

A manual is a kind of technical communication document that contains both written instructions and screenshots of the human-machine interfaces (Office of Information and Technology, 2017). Hardware manuals frequently include clear simplified diagrams. Although user guides are written by programmers, product or project managers, or technical employees, especially in small businesses, it is also authored by a professional writer.

E-learning is a new way of teaching in this new media age. In this era, the e-learning is generally used by the students, considering that the e-learning is simple. E-learning applies electronic technology to access educational curriculum farther of a traditional classroom. In most cases, it assigns to a course, degree, or program delivered completely online.

In an article by SwipeGuide (2019), providing clear and concise work instructions to users will improve operational efficiency, reduce downtime, and increase training procedures. By realizing a digital manual, it will easily understand by the users. It follows by a procedure created by SwipeGuide, a platform where the structure and clarity are the key in instructions.

According to Young (2014), the goal of a digital single-lens reflex (DSLR) camera is to produce high-quality images due to the high number of megapixels as well as the large images sensors housed within the body. It explains that the lower the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) number, the lighter a user need to acquire a proper exposure on your photos, the less noise he or she will see in the final product. Higher ISO levels allow a photographer to capture higher-quality shots in low-light situations, but they also increase the amount of noise in the background of your photos. Image quality is highly dependent on the type of lens a person use.

According to Nguyen and Brancaccio (2018), it makes good business sense to establish a more personal relationship through the instruction manual. Consumers are more likely to feel positive about a brand if they are made to feel good about the goods they have purchased. This shows that the contents are very important in creating the manual, the content should be in order and still related connected to the subject. As stated by Falik (2017), what resulted was a personal user manual, which served as a valuable communication tool for the team as well as a learning experience for her.

According to Avvisati (2014), digital learning is effective when new tools are utilized to prolong study time and practice; as a result, new gadgets can facilitate collaborative learning, which is a dynamic learning environment in which students teach new concepts to one another. This demonstrates how students value and benefit from digital learning.

In the study of Alsadhan et al. (2014), the presentation of multimedia elements like video, audio, graphics, and images has an appeased demand for interactive learning experiences. There are changes in developing and integrating the ways of multimedia elements. It requires a consistent model for the integration of multimedia elements in e-learning systems (Cabbab, 2020).

Figure 1. Outline on how to write a good instruction manual (SwipeGuide, 2019)

Guide is the basic element of every structure where every topic, instruction, and step by step where implemented. Topic is a structure where the users where easily understand what they were reading, it is basically where the starting point of a digital instruction. Instructions are where the users are being instructed. It contains several instructions consist of number of separate instructions. Steps are the complicated description of instructions. It shows the step-by-step process of operating a given wok to the user. In every instruction, there is a clear goal, and that should have a description that always be task-oriented.

Figure 2. ADDIE model of Dominican SnapGuide

Figure 2 shows what the researchers were going to follow. The researchers would analyze and determine the goals of the research. It includes software such as Adobe Illustrator, Adobe Photoshop, Adobe Lightroom, and Adobe Animate. To follow, the researchers would design based from the analysis, using the modern and decent design for the output. The image and layouts were originally made by the researchers. Developing the design after creating a prototype, the researchers would conduct a test.

This study focuses on creating an interactive e-manual for basic and digital photography class of St. Dominic College of Asia. This study can help students to understand and gain knowledge from the interactive e-manual for basic and digital photography class.

Methodology

A descriptive research design is used to describe or observe a certain situation without affecting normal behavior and making accurate predictions about it. The researchers used the quantitative research approach because the researchers required a definite answer to the respondent's feedback or evaluation.

A simple random sampling was also utilized as this will provide an easier mode of data gathering that every student that is available around the campus who took the course subject has the equal opportunity to be chosen as a participant. Since Multimedia Arts students will be most accessible, course photography is chosen as an essential subject.

The researchers used a DSLR camera to take photographs for the layout that will be implemented to the interactive e-manual (Javh et al., 2018). To produce the interactive E-manual, all the contents, images, and objects must be related in basic photography. The lessons of basic and digital photography that will be included to the e-manual are only limited, so the researchers would only use five weeks of basic and digital photography lessons and the progress of the interactive e-manual would be based on the subject syllabus of the professor and no further lessons will be included after that. The researchers used readable fonts for output. In the production of the interactive E-manual, the researchers utilized some fixed kinds of lens and a certain type of DSLR (Canon 1300D) for the layout. Software was used such as Adobe Illustrator, Adobe Lightroom, and Adobe Photoshop for creating the two-dimensional layouts and graphics.

Figure 3. Homepage of Dominican SnapGuide

The researchers used modern style in terms of graphics based on the pastel color palette. It also included five contents: Introduction; Introduction to the principles of photography; The historical background of camera; Understanding the basic parts of camera; Understanding how camera works and operates. The output was saved in 1920x1080 24fps. The manual is interactive, and it was done on Adobe Animate. The output itself was exported into an SWF file and was played using Internet Explorer.

Figure 4. Table of contents and DSLR angle views

A data gathering through research questionnaires was conducted at St. Dominic College of Asia. The researchers considered that all participants must have enrolled in the basic and digital photography and must be still around the campus. Sixty-five (65) students participated in the research study. Through different questionnaires, the researchers would collect information. The researchers will send a request letter to SDCA for permission or verification to conduct a survey.

After the school approves, the researchers could start their survey by testing the interactive e-manual and distributing the questionnaire to the participants that have been enrolled in basic and digital photography for the Academic Year 2018-2019. The researchers used structured questions that should be related on the evaluation of the interactive e-manual of basic and digital photography. Frequency and percentage distribution was used to the effectiveness of the interactive e-manual.

Results and Discussion

The researchers conducted a demographic profile of the participants. The researchers conducted a two-part survey. The first part is to rate the level of response to the interactive e-manual for basic and digital photography class according to the given criteria: if it does identify the basic parts of the camera, understand the importance of principles of photography, explain the historical background of camera, able to adapt with various situations by using necessary camera lens and settings, alters and manipulates camera's exposure triangle and white balance to enhance image quality, and applies good practices in photography. The researchers provided a comment box for the participants to write whatever they want towards the project.

Based on the project Dominican SnapGuide, a basic and interactive e-manual, the multimedia elements used were images, text, and animation. The images were implemented to the e-manual are original photographs from the researchers, whereas some photographs shot from different camera angles such as rule of thirds and factors when considering taking good photographs.

The researchers also used different camera settings like different shots of ISO, shutter speed, white balance, and aperture. It also includes some photographs of different kinds of camera lenses and types of cameras. For the text, the researchers added a context for the introduction and summary of each lesson, the definitions of different types of camera and lenses, the history of photography, the context of the camera parts and buttons, and some photography tips. The researchers provided the information in the project and some of the contents came from reliable sources like books and the internet. For the animation, the researchers composed some moving elements in the project so the user will be entertained and to make the project more interactive like rotating the aperture logo in the home screen, creating a mouse cursor moving towards the DSLR so the user can be aware that each button in the project are clickable, and showing or hiding an image or text element for each button.

The researchers gathered the data in the campus. To interpret the equations the researchers scaled one (1) to five (5) to determine the range of the answered questionnaires (1=master, 2=professional, 3=advance, 4=amateur, and 5=beginner).

Table 1. Question 1: Identify the basic parts of the camera

Categories	Count	Distribution
Master	18	40%
Professional	18	40%
Advance	4	8.89%
Amateur	4	8.89%
Beginner	1	2.22%
Total	45	100%

Identify the basic parts of the camera. Forty percent (40%) of the respondents answered master and with the same equivalent, respondents also answered professional that the target respondents can identify the basic parts of the camera in the interactive e-manual.

Table 2. Question 2: Understand the importance of principles of photography

Categories	Count	Distribution
Master	20	44.5%
Professional	12	26.7%
Advance	10	22.22%
Amateur	2	4.44%
Beginner	1	2.22%
Total	45	100%

Understand the importance of principles of photography. The respondents understand the importance of the principles of photography in the interactive e-manual with a 44.44% of the respondents answered master. This means that students have reduced the complexity and focused their attention on the most important elements appear to encourage users to actively explore and make associations between them on their own (Moser et al., 2012).

Table 3. Question 3: Explain the historical background of camera

Categories	Count	Distribution
Master	14	31.11%
Professional	19	42.22%
Advance	7	15.56%
Amateur	5	11.11%
Beginner	0	0%
Total	45	100%

Explain the historical background of camera. Among all students, 31.11% of the target respondents answered master with the highest rating on the survey questions corresponds with, that the respondents easily understand of how the interactive e-manual explain the historical background of camera.

Table 4. Question 4: Able to adapt with various situations by using necessary camera lens and settings

Categories	Count	Distribution
Master	18	40%
Professional	16	35.56%
Advance	5	11.11%
Amateur	5	11.11%
Beginner	1	2.22%
Total	45	100%

Able to adapt with various situations by using necessary camera lens and settings. With the highest equivalent, 40% answered master that they were able to adapt with various situations by using necessary camera lens and settings.

Table 5. Question 5: Alters and manipulates camera’s exposure triangle and white balance to enhance image quality

Categories	Count	Distribution
Master	21	46.67%
Professional	13	28.89%
Advance	7	15.56%
Amateur	3	11.11%
Beginner	1	2.22%
Total	45	100%

Alters and manipulates camera’s exposure triangle and white balance to enhance image quality. Of the total respondents, 46.67% of the students answered master that the respondents alter and manipulates camera’s exposure triangle and white balance to enhance image quality with the help of the interactive e-manual

Table 6. Question 6: Applies good practices in photography

Categories	Count	Distribution
Master	25	55.56%
Professional	10	22.22%
Advance	7	15.56%
Amateur	2	4.44%
Beginner	1	2.22%
Total	45	100%

Applies good practices in photography. 55.56% answered master with the highest rating on the survey questions corresponds to the statement that the target respondents apply good practices in photography in using the interactive E-manual.

Table 7. Comments on the impact of the interactive e-manual

Comments	Count	Distribution
Positive comments	38	84.44%
Negative comments	7	15.56%
Total	45	100%

The researchers used the quantitative method to determine the positive and negative answers of the target respondents based on the impact of the interactive e-manual. The table shows that thirty-eight (38) of the respondents with an equivalent of 84.44% gave positive comments to the interactive e-manual, while seven (7) out of forty-five (45) respondents with an equivalent of 15.56% have negative comments to the project.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The project, Dominican SnapGuide: An Interactive E-Manual for Basic and Digital Photography Class achieved the main objectives through survey and the researchers applied the needed elements for the output to be finished. The researchers conclude that animation, image, and text were the multimedia elements included in the interactive e-manual; therefore, based on the production, these multimedia elements are the basic elements needed for the project to be finished.

The researchers conclude that the interactive e-manual for basic and digital photography class has highly reached its standard accordingly to the result from the overall result of responses of the participants toward the project. It shows that the interactive e-manual does identify the basic parts of a camera, can understand the importance of principles of photography, can clearly explain the historical background of a camera, and is able to adapt with various situations by using necessary camera lens and settings like ISO, shutter speed, white balance, and apertures. The e-manual alters and manipulates camera's exposure triangle and white balance to enhance image quality and applies good practices in photography.

In terms of the impact, the interactive manual project provided a positive impact to the respondents who were then utilized the said project. This can be reflected that the output itself can be useful in providing interactive based learning to students with basic and digital photography courses.

Based on the said project, the images were implemented to the e-manual are original photographs from the researchers. Some photographs were shot from different camera angles such as rule of thirds and factors when considering of taking good photographs.

The researchers recommended that for those who have good skills and knowledge in animation, more improvement of the project should be utilized including additional tips and guidelines about using different kinds of camera settings. An additional animation for the scenes should be involved especially if the content needs an animation. More images should be added like different kinds of lenses, as well as mini-quiz at the end of every lesson. The researchers suggested that the interactive e-manual should be presented in five (5) weeks basic and digital photography class in the future.

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